

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF METHOTEXATE TRANSDERMAL PATCH BY USING VARIOUS POLYMERS RESEARCH ARTICLE

G. Himaja^{*}, L. Nikhitha, P. Chitra, A. Akshaya, M. Sindhu

B Pharmacy Student, Sri Lakshmi Venkateshwara Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Proddatur, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh.

Article Received on 29 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 19 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 01 March 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18798243>

*Corresponding Author

G. Himaja

B. Pharmacy Student, Sri Lakshmi
Venkateshwara Institute of
Pharmaceutical Sciences, Proddatur,
Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh.

How to cite this Article: G. Himaja^{*}, L. Nikhitha P., Chitra A. Akshaya M. Sindhu. (2026). Formulation and Evaluation of Methotexate Transdermal Patch By Using Various Polymers Research Article. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(5), 740-748.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this research is to prepare Methotrexate transdermal patches were formulated using HPMC and PVP as film forming polymers. patches were prepared by solvent casting method and evaluated for physicochemical properties. In order to obtain best optimised products. 9 different formulations were developed different polymers like HPMC, PVP, ethanol, glycerine dissolving in minimal amount of acceptable solvent. the prepared patches evaluate to physical appearance, determination of drug content, in vitro drug release. formulation F9 contain HPMC and PVP (500) shows maximum drug release, produced flexible, smooth films with good mechanical properties. compared to other formulations.

KEYWORDS: Methotrexate, Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (HPMC), Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), Ethanol, glycerine.

Novel Drug delivery system

Novel drug delivery system [NDDS] refers to the approaches formulation technologies and systems for transporting a pharmaceutical compound in the body as needed to safely achieve its desired therapeutic effects. NDDS is a system for delivery of drug other than conventional drug delivery system. NDDS is a combination of advance technique and new dosage form which are far better than conventional dosage form. A novel drug delivery system plays

important role to enhancing the therapeutic efficacy, reducing toxicity increasing patient compliance and enabling entirely new medical treatment.^[1]

Transdermal Patches

A **transdermal patch** is a medicated adhesive patch that is placed on the skin to deliver a specific dose of medication through the skin and into the bloodstream. An advantage of transdermal drug delivery route over other types of medication delivery (such as oral, topical, intravenous, or intramuscular) is that the patch provides a controlled release of the medication into the patient, usually through either a porous membrane covering a reservoir of medication or through body heat melting thin layers of medication embedded in the adhesive. The main disadvantage to transdermal delivery systems stems from the fact that the skin is a very effective barrier; as a result, only medications whose molecules are small enough to penetrate the skin can be delivered by this method. The first commercially available prescription patch was approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration in December 1979. These patches administer transdermal red scopolamine for motion sickness.^[2,3,4,5]

Cancer

“Cancer refers to any one of a large number of diseases characterized by the development of abnormal cells that divide uncontrollably and have the ability to infiltrate and destroy normal body tissue”. Cancer is caused by the changes to DNA. Most of the Cancer causing DNA changes occurs in section of DNA called genes. These changes are also called genetic changes.^[6]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Methotrexate: Methotrexate, is a chemotherapy agent and immune-system suppressant. It is used to treat cancer, autoimmune diseases, and ectopic pregnancies. It is an antimetabolite

Polyvinylpyrrolidone: Used as a solubilizing agent, which promotes faster dissolution and improve drug absorption. **Hydroxypropylmethylcellulose [HPMC]:** It act as a matrix forming polymer that controls drug release.

Polyethylene glycol: it act as a plasticizer and improving the flexibility and adhesion of the patch. **Ethanol:** Act as a penetration enhancer and increasing the skin permeability.

Formulation Table

Ingredients	Batches								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Amount of MTX	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
polyvinylpyrrolidone PVP (mg)	100	100	100	100	100	200	300	400	500
HPMC(mg)	100	200	300	400	500	100	100	100	100
PEG 400	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Ethanol	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Distilled water v/v ml	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Preparation Of Transdermal Patch By Solvent Casting Method

Transdermal patch was prepared by a solvent casting method. Precisely weigh the amount of polymer and soak in solvent 24 hrs before the preparation in a prescribed amount of solvent in a beaker. After soaking the polymer by using the glass rod gently mix the polymer solution to form thick viscous solution with less air entrapment. In case of any air bubbles are entrapped in the solution by using sonicator remove their bubbles. Weigh the approximate amount of the drug and transfer it into the mortar and made fine powder and transfer the powdered drug into polymer solution and make clear viscous solution. Transfer the solvent in a petridish which is pre applied with a lubricant. Place the petridish in a room temperature for 24 hrs to remove the moisture content and to form thin film. After forming a thin film it off from the petridish with the help of the ointment spatula and store for the further evaluation tests.

Evaluation test**weight uniformity**

S.No	Formulation code	Weight uniformity			
		Trial1	Trial2	Trial3	average
1	F1	0.52	0.48	0.46	0.48
2	F2	0.44	0.42	0.40	0.42
3	F3	0.47	0.45	0.43	0.45
4	F4	0.38	0.35	0.33	0.35
5	F5	0.39	0.37	0.32	0.36
6	F6	0.33	0.28	0.25	0.28
7	F7	0.35	0.29	0.25	0.29
8	F8	0.29	0.27	0.24	0.26
9	F9	0.20	0.20	0.18	0.20

Folding Endurance

S. No	Formulation Code	Folding endurance			
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Average
1	F1	312	310	290	307
2	F2	310	305	300	305
3	F3	185	176	172	177
4	F4	290	287	283	286
5	F5	250	244	238	244
6	F6	234	230	228	230
7	F7	256	248	237	247
8	F8	195	190	185	190
9	F9	320	310	305	311

Percentage Moisture Absorption

S no	Formulation Code	% moisture absorption			
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	average
1	F1	4.03	4.13	4.03	4.06
2	F2	4.29	4.19	4.24	4.24
3	F3	3.35	3.15	3.20	3.23
4	F4	3.97	3.92	3.87	3.92
5	F5	3.88	3.19	3.89	3.65
6	F6	3.93	3.84	3.72	3.83
7	F7	2.63	2.44	2.02	2.36

8	F8	2.23	2.19	2.08	2.16
9	F9	2.46	2.43	2.37	2.42

Percentage Moisture Loss

S No	Formulation code	Percentage moisture loss			
		Trial1	Trial2	Trial3	average
1	F1	8.56	8.53	9.02	8.70
2	F2	7.22	9.36	10.27	8.95
3	F3	5.04	5.07	5.05	5.05
4	F4	2.75	2.27	4.23	3.75
5	F5	3.89	3.76	2.67	3.44
6	F6	2.87	2.78	2.47	2.70
7	F7	2.98	3.25	4.46	3.56
8	F8	4.20	4.15	4.05	4.13
9	F9	2.25	2.19	2.03	2.15

Water vapour transmission rate

S no	Formulation code	Water vapour transmission rate			
		Trial1	Trial2	Trial3	average
1	F1	0.0037	0.0030	0.0028	0.0031
2	F2	0.0030	0.0025	0.0020	0.0025
3	F3	0.0025	0.0022	0.0020	0.0022
4	F4	0.0032	0.0025	0.0023	0.0026

5	F5	0.0038	0.0044	0.0035	0.0039
6	F6	0.0033	0.0030	0.0025	0.0029
7	F7	0.0038	0.0035	0.0028	0.0033
8	F8	0.0044	0.0040	0.0038	0.0040
9	F9	0.0040	0.0044	0.0036	0.004

Tensile strength

S. No	Formulation code	Tensile strength			
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	average
1	F1	3.30	3.16	3.10	3.18
2	F2	2.89	2.91	3.05	2.95
3	F3	2.19	2.14	2.11	2.14
4	F4	3.20	3.29	3.20	3.23
5	F5	3.25	3.33	3.23	3.27
6	F6	3.44	3.39	3.33	3.38
7	F7	3.41	3.38	3.32	3.37
8	F8	2.21	2.18	2.13	2.17
9	F9	3.85	3.90	3.75	3.83

Drug Content

S. No	Formulation Code	Concentration (mg/cm ²)	% Drug Content
1	F1	1.82±0.054	81
2	F2	1.177±0.073	84
3	F3	1.028±0.012	80
4	F4	1.078±0.045	90
5	F5	1.067±0.037	90.52
6	F6	1.058±.022	89
7	F7	1.047±0.019	87.04
8	F8	1.033±0.017	85.54
9	F9	1.87±0.075	98

In vitro drug distribution study

S. No	time [hrs]	Percentage cumulative drug release								
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	1	8.057	12.147	13.586	15.49	11.754	11.718	20.452	25.586	28.574
2	2	12.162	16.056	16.292	21.52	18.748	17.711	25.446	30.570	47.721
3	3	18.247	20.253	18.302	21.58	27.752	19.670	30.389	33.567	68.281
4	4	20.123	32.302	22.375	34.63	30.650	24.674	34.286	35.556	77.712
5	5	23.154	37.348	26.382	41.72	41.623	28.654	37.263	39.543	85.816
6	6	29.562	45.370	30.421	48.76	46.604	35.523	45.246	45.537	90.886
7	7	33.325	48.412	37.404	55.88	51.520	49.519	50.223	51.529	95.890
8	8	47.462	52.423	42.435	59.92	53.590	51.500	54.219	57.513	
9	9	55.578	57.504	47.482	62.256	57.516	56.450	59.200	60.502	
10	10	60.222	63.526	59.498	69.278	60.498	58.423	65.192	67.470	
11	11	63.812	67.573	66.512	72.306	65.420	64.320	67.176	71.350	
12	12	68.421	71.589	73.533	75.330	69.300	67.290	70.163	77.420	

CONCLUSION

The methotrexate transdermal patches showed good physical, mechanical, and stability characteristics. The tensile strength and WVTR values indicated strong and stable patches suitable for skin application. Transdermal patches were prepared by solvent casting method. We prepared total 9 formulations with different ratios among all those formulations F9 contain HPMC and PVP (500mg). According to evaluation tests F9 shows best drug release profile. Therefore, we concluded F9 is the best formulation.

REFERENCES

1. Charman W. N., Chan K., Finin BC & Chairman SA. Drug delivery: a key factor in realising the full therapeutic potential of drug. *Drug development research*, 1999; 46: 316-27.
2. Veerabadran, Nalinkanth G.; Price, Ronald R.; Lvov, Yuri M. (April 2007). "Clay Nanotubes for Encapsulation and Sustained Release of Drugs". *Nano*. 02(2): 115– 120. doi:10.1142/s1793292007000441. ISSN 1793-2920.
3. FDA approves rolapitant to prevent chemotherapy-induced nausea". *The Pharmaceutical Journal*. 2015. doi:10.1211/pj.2015.20069288. ISSN 2053-6186.
4. Segal, Marian. "Patches, Pumps and Timed Release: New Ways to Deliver Drugs". Food and Drug Administration. Archived from the original on February 10, 2007. Retrieved February 24, 2007.
5. "FDA approves scopolamine patch to prevent peri-operative nausea" Food and Drug Administration. November 10, 1997. Archived from the original on December 19, 2006; Retrieved February 12, 2007.
6. D R. Rachana Chaudhary (Department of microbiology), Introduction and description of cancer, Mar 4, 2024
7. "Methotrexate". The American Society of Health-System Pharmacists. Archived from the original on 8 October 2016. Retrieved 22 August 2016
8. "Trexall, Rheumatrex (methotrexate) dosing, indications, interactions, adverse effects, and more". Medscape Reference. WebMD. Archived from the original on 8 February 2014. Retrieved 12 April 2014
9. Inoue K, Yuasa H: Molecular basis for pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of methotrexate in rheumatoid arthritis therapy. *Drug Metab Pharmacokinet*. 2014; 29(1): 12-9. Epub 2013 Nov 26 REFE

10. Bannwarth B, Labat L, Moride Y, Schaefferbeke T (January 1994). "Methotrexate in rheumatoid arthritis. An update". *Drugs*, 47(1): 25–50. doi:10.2165/00003495-199447010-00003. PMID 7510620. S2CID 46974070.
11. Rajagopalan PT, Zhang Z, Mc Court L, Dwyer M, Benkovic S J, Hammes GG (October 2002). "Interaction of dihydrofolate reductase with methotrexate: ensemble and single-molecule kinetics". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*.
12. Goodsell DS (August 1999). "The molecular perspective: methotrexate". *The Oncologist*. 4(4): 340–1. doi:10.1634/theoncologist.4-4-340. PMID 10476546.
13. Brayfield A, ed. (6 January 2014). "Methotrexate". *Martindale: The Complete Drug Reference*. Pharmaceutical Press. Retrieved 12 April 2014.
14. Haaf, F.; Sanner, A.; Straub, F. (1985). "Polymers of N-Vinylpyrrolidone: Synthesis, Characterization and Uses". *Polymer Journal*, 17: 143–152. doi:10.1295/polymj.17.143.
15. Povidones, Copovidones, and Crospovidones for Pharmaceutical Products". BASF Pharma. Retrieved 2022; 06-11.
16. Bühler, Volker (2005). *Polyvinylpyrrolidone Excipients for Pharmaceuticals: Povidone, Crospovidone and Copovidone*. Berlin, Heidelberg, New York: Springer. 1–254. doi:10.1007/b138598. ISBN 978-3540234128.
17. "Soothe Hydration Lubricant Eye Drops". Bausch & Lomb. Retrieved Sep 27, 2017.
18. Inactive Ingredients in FDA Approved Drugs. FDA/Center for Drug Evaluation and Research, Office of Generic Drugs, Division of Labeling and Program Support. Database Update Frequency: Quarterly. Data Through: January 6, 2010. Database Last Updated: January 13, 2010 – search on povidone for list of approved items
19. <https://www.lookchem.com/cas-900/9004-65-3.html>
20. Al-Tabakha MM: HPMC capsules: current status and future prospects. *J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2010; 13(3): 428-42.